

ANALYSIS OF EDUCATION POLICY IN REDUCE THE PHENOMENON OF STUDENTS DROPOUTS IN VARIOUS REGIONS IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

The phenomenon of school dropouts in Indonesia is a complex issue influenced by various multidimensional factors. This study aims to identify the factors causing school dropouts and analyze government policies to reduce the dropout rate. The method used is *Systematic Literature Review* (SLR). The analysis results show that economic factors are the most dominant cause, mainly due to limited family income, high education costs, and the demand for children to contribute to the family economy. In addition, social and cultural environmental factors, such as low public awareness of the importance of education, certain cultural values, and the influence of the surrounding environment, also contribute to increasing the dropout rate. Individual factors, such as low motivation to learn, interest, and academic ability of students, are also factors in dropping out of school. On the other hand, the government has implemented various policies to reduce the dropout rate, including the School Operational Assistance (BOS/BOSP), the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP), the free education and 12-year compulsory education policies, and regional-based programs supported by the commitment of local governments. Furthermore, strengthening data collection systems, social interventions, and cross-sector collaboration are also important strategies in addressing this issue. Although these policies have had a positive impact, their implementation still faces various obstacles, such as inaccurate targeting, uneven distribution of aid, and suboptimal coordination between institutions. Therefore, strengthening policy implementation, increasing public awareness, and a more comprehensive and sustainable approach are needed to reduce the dropout rate in Indonesia.

Keywords: *dropout, factors causing school dropouts, education policy and government policy.*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a right for every citizen and plays a vital role in improving the quality of human resources and driving national progress. In Indonesia, the government has formulated various education policies to ensure equitable access and improve quality, such as the compulsory education program, School Operational Assistance (BOS), the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP), the Smart Indonesia Card (KIP), and various other social assistance programs. However, in its implementation, several obstacles remain that hinder the achievement of these goals, one of which is the problem of students dropping out of school.

School dropout remains a serious issue in various regions of Indonesia, both urban and rural. The causes are diverse, including economic, social, and geographic issues, as well as a lack of support from the surrounding community. (Khairani et al., 2025). Apart from that, it is also caused by low interest and motivation to learn, academic difficulties, promiscuity, which results in early marriage, health problems, and limited access to educational facilities and infrastructure. Disparities in development between regions also contribute to school dropouts, such as difficult road access and remote schools, which prevent all students from having the same opportunity to complete their education at a certain level.

In an effort to address this issue, the government has launched various policies. These policies are expected to reduce the dropout rate by providing financial assistance and improving the quality of educational services. However, their effectiveness still requires further study, particularly regarding their implementation in various regions with varying characteristics and challenges. In this regard, analyzing education policies is crucial to assess the extent to which implemented policies are able to address the dropout problem. This analysis covers various aspects, from planning and implementation to evaluation, to their impact on the sustainability of students' education.

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This allows for the identification of weaknesses and opportunities for improvement in existing policies. Based on this explanation, this article aims to examine education policies addressing the dropout phenomenon in various regions of Indonesia. The results of this study are expected to contribute to the formulation of more effective, responsive, and equitable education policies to reduce dropout rates in the future.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Education Policy Concept

Education policy can be understood as a series of decisions used as a guideline in the implementation of education to achieve predetermined goals. According to Edi Suharto, public policy is a decision formulated by the government to address various problems faced by society. In the educational realm, policy plays a crucial role in improving access, quality, and equity of educational services. In line with this opinion, Nanang Fattah argues that education policy is part of education management, serving as a guideline and direction for educational decision-making. Therefore, education policy is not merely normative but also has an operational dimension that is realized through implementation on the ground.

While the central government's education policy in Indonesia applies equally to all regions, various regions have different policies designed to reduce school dropout rates. The government's efforts and role in improving the quality of education in Indonesia are important.

We can see this in Indonesia through the issuance of various policies, one of which is the 12-year compulsory education program. Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 80 of 2013 concerning universal secondary education was formulated as a foundation emphasizing the government's obligation to ensure the provision of education. This regulation also directs the effective implementation of the 12-year compulsory education program.(Fadel & Aini, 2025).

2. Definition and Factors Causing School Dropouts

Dropping out of school is a situation where students are unable to complete their education at a certain level. According to Mulyasa, this condition is an indicator of low educational quality and a suboptimal education system in maintaining student learning continuity. Various factors can contribute to dropout. Suyatno stated that economic factors are the dominant cause, along with social factors, learning motivation, and family environment. In addition, internal factors such as low interest in learning and external factors, such as unsupportive school policies, also contribute to dropout. The analysis of Pallulungan's research shows that the number of school dropouts in Indonesia varies significantly across provinces. Provinces with larger populations tend to have higher absolute dropout rates. Furthermore, high school dropout rates are higher than elementary and junior high schools.(Palullungan et al., 2026) Economic factors are the biggest cause of school dropouts Economic constraints make it difficult for families to meet educational needs, both directly and indirectly, potentially leading children to stop their education early. Rambey (2022) demonstrated a significant relationship between a family's economic condition and a child's educational attainment. This finding confirms that family economic constraints significantly impact a child's educational sustainability, particularly in areas with limited access to education.

In several regions in Indonesia, one of the fundamental inhibiting factors is geographical conditions and circumstances, such as those in Central Bangka Regency which are less supportive in efforts to reduce the number of school dropouts.(Suryati et al., 2025)These geographical conditions include isolated settlements, those far from educational centers, inadequate road access, and some areas that are even difficult to reach because they are separated by forests and rivers. Talakua emphasized the importance of stakeholders in addressing school dropouts in Ambon City, including families, especially parents. The role of families is crucial as it determines the success of a child's development and education. With parental involvement, children will develop a positive attitude toward learning, leading to good grades and enabling them to continue on to higher levels of education and complete their education.(Talakua, 2018).

Parental awareness is also crucial in education, as it can impact a child's future. Raising children's or students' awareness to stay in school requires parental support and encouragement. If parents care about their children's education, they will undoubtedly continue to motivate them to continue. Conversely, if parents don't care about their children's education, they will lack the motivation to continue. The phenomenon of school dropouts is a serious problem in the national education system because it directly impacts the low level of public education and hampers human resource development. The high dropout rate also has implications for the low Human Development Index (HDI) and increases social and economic vulnerability in the community. Dropping out of

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school does not occur in isolation but is the result of the interaction of various factors, such as family economic hardship, cultural traditions and values, and systemic barriers in the provision of education. In the context of a transitional society, these factors are interconnected and create conditions that make it difficult for students to maintain the continuity of formal education.(Zebua, 2024).

3. Government Policy to Reduce School Dropouts

The Indonesian government has established various policies to address the issue of school dropouts. Programs such as compulsory education, School Operational Assistance (BOS), and the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP) are a manifestation of the government's efforts to expand access to education and a form of government intervention in improving access to education. The central government also issued a 12-year compulsory education program in 2013 as a continuation of the previous program, namely 9 years of compulsory education. The aim of this continuation program is to maintain the success and continuity of the previous program, as well as to prepare Indonesia's golden generation in 2045. The development of a country requires quality human resources as its driving force. This can be achieved through education. However, improving the quality of human resources through education is still hampered by various factors, such as environmental, physical, and non-physical factors. Completion of 12 years of compulsory education is influenced by two main factors, namely internal factors (within the student) and external factors (outside the student).(HG Sutisna et al., 2025).

Tilaar (2012) stated that education policy should focus on equalizing learning opportunities and improving the quality of human resources. A policy can be considered effective if it responds to community needs and is adaptive to the dynamics of social change. However, the success of such a policy is largely determined by its implementation on the ground. Therefore, harmonious cooperation between the government, schools, and the community is necessary to support the achievement of education policy goals. In Aswar et al.'s research, there are different factors that cause school dropouts, namely a culture that does not prioritize school. Strategies for dealing with dropouts must be designed by considering the main, multidimensional causes, ranging from economic to cultural aspects. Preventive and curative efforts need to be implemented simultaneously, for example through the provision of scholarships, transportation subsidies, educational equality programs such as Kejar Paket A/B/C, and special programs such as "Jemput Anak Sekolah" (Pick Up School Children) which aims to return children to formal education. Furthermore, the active involvement of village governments, schools, parents, and civil society is essential to create a more inclusive and sustainable education ecosystem.(Aswar et al., 2025).

In East Kotawaringin Regency, Central Kalimantan Province, the strategy to anticipate and handle ATS, the Regional Government with BAPPEDA as the coordinator, coordinated the Education Office in implementing activities to handle dropouts by coordinating and synergizing with TLD officers in the implementation of ATS data collection in East Kotawaringin. The persuasive approach of field officers, made school-age children who were not in school (ATS) who were successfully registered willing to return to learning either through formal channels (schools) or through non-formal institutions such as the Learning Activity Center (SKB), Community Learning Activity Center (PKBM), and Course and Training Institute (LKP).(Andayani, 2021).

4. Implementation and Evaluation of Education Policy

Policy implementation is a crucial stage in determining the success or failure of a policy. According to George C. Edwards III, four main factors influence the success of policy implementation: communication, resource availability, the disposition or attitude of implementers, and bureaucratic structure. Next, a policy evaluation is conducted to assess the extent to which the policy has achieved its stated objectives. Policy evaluation aims to provide accurate and reliable information regarding a policy's performance, thus providing a basis for future policy improvements. The results of research by Sutisna et al. in Sukabumi show that the Education Office has implemented several strategic policies, such as the Dropout Tracking Program (PAPS) to reach students who have dropped out or are at risk of dropping out, family mentoring, strengthening the Equivalency Education program, and mapping areas prone to APS. The implementation process involves UPTD, guidance counselors, school principals, village officials, RT/RW, and community leaders, and is supported by the preparation of SOPs for handling APS which are socialized to all educational units.(A. Sutisna et al., 2025). The results of Edrial et al.'s research show that the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Program at SMA Negeri 1 Utan, when linked to effectiveness criteria, can be said to be effective because there have never been any cases of students dropping out of school. In terms of efficiency, it is still less efficient. The

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efforts made by the implementers have been maximized, but in terms of budget management, it is still inefficient. In terms of equality, the benefits of the program are still not evenly distributed to the target group. In terms of responsiveness, it is good. In terms of accuracy, this program is still not appropriate, because the implementers do not receive any compensation for carrying out their duties. (Edrial et al., 2022) Meanwhile, in the city of Cilegon, the Free Education Service has succeeded in reducing the number of children not attending school (ATS). One of the local government's strategies to reduce the number of school dropouts in Latimojong Village, Buntu Batu District, Enrekang Regency, South Sulawesi Province, is to provide scholarships and financial assistance. Scholarships are awarded to students from low-income families to enable them to continue their education, while the School Operational Assistance Program (BOS) provides funds to schools to reduce education costs, making them more affordable for all. In addition, there are social and welfare programs, such as social assistance to improve family welfare and school health programs to ensure children receive good health care and nutrition. Public awareness and participation are increased through campaigns that highlight the importance of education and the negative impacts of dropping out of school. Parents are also involved in the educational process and decision-making regarding their children's education. (Lorensa et al., 2024)

METHOD

This study applies the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method to comprehensively examine various educational policies addressing the dropout phenomenon in Indonesia. This method was chosen because of its ability to systematically and objectively identify, assess, and integrate previous research findings. The research process was conducted through three main stages: planning, implementation, and reporting. In the planning stage, researchers formulated research questions and established search keywords, such as school dropout, factors causing school dropout, education policy, government policy, and access to education. The implementation stage included a literature search from various scientific sources, such as Google Scholar, Garuda (Digital Reference Garuda), and accredited national journal. The articles obtained were then selected based on their suitability to the research focus and reviewed for policy substance, implementation, and effectiveness in addressing the school dropout phenomenon. In the reporting stage, the collected data was analyzed using qualitative descriptive techniques by grouping, comparing, and synthesizing the research findings. The analysis was then presented in narrative form to provide a comprehensive overview of the effectiveness of education policies in addressing the dropout phenomenon.

The SLR approach was chosen because it provides a structured, open, and replicable framework for reviewing scientific literature, thus revealing research trends, research gaps, and theoretical and practical contributions to higher education policy studies (Rifai et al., 2025). The implementation of the systematic literature review in this study refers to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 guidelines, which emphasize the importance of transparency in the identification, selection, feasibility evaluation, and synthesis stages of scientific articles. Through the application of the SLR method, this research is expected to be able to produce comprehensive findings based on scientific evidence, so that it can contribute to the development of more effective and sustainable education policies in addressing the phenomenon of school dropouts and providing more targeted policy recommendations.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Previous research

Based on the results of the analysis of the literature that has been traced, the following data were obtained.

No	Location	Objective	Method	Strategy/ Policy	Causative factor	Inhibiting Factors	Results/Impact	Recommendation
1	Central Bangka	Analyzing government strategies to reduce school dropout rates	Descriptive qualitative	Political will: priority programs, scholarships, school construction, regulations	Economy, access to education, impact of the pandemic	Geographical area, difficult access	The government's efforts are quite strong but not yet optimal.	Village & business collaboration, data monitoring
2	Enrekang (Latimojong Village)	Reviewing local government strategies	Qualitative	Multi-sector approach, educational assistance, infrastructure improvement	Economy, lack of parental attention, family conditions	Limited budget, road access, land	Collaboration between government and society has a positive impact	Strengthen cooperation and access to education
3	Cilegon	Assessing the impact of free education	Descriptive qualitative	12 years of compulsory education, "Sekola Maning Lur" program	Economy, low motivation, environment, family	Infrastructure, school access	The dropout rate is low, but not yet optimal.	Optimization of programs and internal student factors
4	Sumbawa (SMAN 1 Utan)	Evaluation of the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP)	Descriptive qualitative	Educational funding assistance (PIP)	Poverty, education costs	Uneven distribution, weak administration	Effective in preventing school dropouts, but not yet efficient	Improvement of distribution and management
5	Sukabumi	Analysis of APS policy implementation	Descriptive qualitative	PAPS, family support, equal education	Economy, early marriage, culture, low motivation	Inaccurate data, cultural resistance	The program is running but not yet optimal	

2. Factors causing school dropouts in various regions in Indonesia

a. Economic Factors

The phenomenon of school dropouts is mostly caused by economic factors. As is the case in Dumoga District, Bolaang Mongondow Regency, North Sulawesi, economic factors are one of the main factors

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affecting the continuation of a child's education. Research in Pusian Village revealed that the economic conditions of families, particularly those working as farmers, significantly influence a child's decision to continue or discontinue their education. The majority of the population in the area works in the agricultural sector with relatively low and unstable incomes. This situation creates limitations in meeting children's educational needs, such as transportation costs, school supplies, and other supporting needs. Pusian Village faces an increasing number of school dropouts due to various factors, particularly inadequate economic conditions. This significantly impacts parents' ability to support their children's education, especially at higher levels. Among the various obstacles, economic factors are among the most dominant, with limited income, lack of stable employment opportunities, and low skill levels often being the root causes. (Andale et al., 2024). This also aligns with Zebua's research findings that socioeconomic challenges remain the most significant barrier to educational attainment in the Nias Islands. Poverty forces many families to prioritize their own survival over long-term investment in education. School-related costs, such as tuition, uniforms, and transportation, are cited as major contributors to the dropout rate. Furthermore, many children are required to work to supplement the family income, leaving little time or energy for school. (Zebua, 2024).

Although the government has provided various educational assistance programs, their implementation has not been able to fully address family economic challenges. In fact, parents' utilization of educational assistance remains suboptimal, resulting in a less than optimal impact on the sustainability of children's education. Economic pressures also encourage children to participate in family economic activities from an early age. Many children choose to help their parents work in agriculture or other jobs to supplement the family income. This indirectly reduces learning time and lowers children's motivation to attend school, ultimately leading to their dropping out. This situation indicates economic pressures that cause children to prioritize short-term needs over education as a long-term investment. Furthermore, economic constraints also influence parents' mindsets and motivations regarding their children's education. In some cases, parents provide little encouragement for their children to continue their education, prioritizing meeting basic daily needs. As a result, children's interest in school declines, especially after completing elementary or junior high school.

This finding aligns with various other studies showing that family economic conditions are a dominant factor in school dropout, primarily due to limited educational costs and daily living expenses. Therefore, it can be concluded that the problem of school dropout is not solely related to individual factors, but is also influenced by family economic conditions and the social environment.

b. Social and Cultural Environmental Factors

The social and cultural environment in which students grow and develop includes family, society, social values, and cultural customs that shape individual thought patterns and behavior towards education. The social and cultural environment also influences children and families' decisions to continue their education. Certain cultural values, social demands, and geographic conditions can hinder participation in formal education. Zebua (2024) revealed that cultural traditions and community mindsets towards education in the Nias Islands region are among the factors driving school dropout. This condition indicates that community perceptions of education play a significant role in determining children's educational success. Khairani et al. (2025) added that the mismatch between local norms and the formal education system creates social dysfunction that impacts the increasing dropout rate. Therefore, education policies need to consider the social and cultural context of the local community to be more effective and inclusive. The community has a significant influence on children's education. Communities that care about the importance of education will always provide a positive social culture for children's development. Meanwhile, communities that do not care about the importance of education will be indifferent to their development. This attitude of community indifference towards the world of education will contribute to the increasing dropout rate (Rokhmaniyah et al. 2022).

c. Individual Factors and Motivation

Dropping out of school is not only influenced by external factors such as economic and environmental factors, but is also largely determined by individual factors, particularly those related to students' learning motivation, interests, attitudes, and mindsets toward education. Individual factors refer to students' personal characteristics that influence their behavior, decisions, and continued participation in formal education. Individual factors include psychological and personal aspects of students, such as academic ability, self-

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confidence, discipline, attitudes toward school, and the ability to manage learning pressure. According to educational theory, students who experience ongoing academic difficulties tend to experience decreased self-confidence and feel unable to participate in the learning process, which ultimately increases the risk of dropping out. Individual factors that influence dropout include low abilities, making students feel it is difficult to complete their education, the person concerned is indeed willing to be educated again due to low abilities, or it could also be because the person concerned simply does not want to learn, school is considered no longer interesting to the student. Thus, the factors suspected of causing children to drop out of school are the child's motivation.(Wildatu Syarofah, 2021).Yaneri's (2022) research also identified internal factors as a cause of school dropout. While dislike of school is a factor contributing to students dropping out, researchers obtained information from Fajar and Yulianto about their reasons for not liking school and deciding to drop out. According to Fajar, he decided to drop out because he was lazy and had no desire to go back to school. He was also afraid of being punished by teachers, which led him to drop out and work to help his parents.

3. Government Policy to Reduce School Dropouts

The issue of school dropouts is a strategic issue in educational development that requires government policy intervention. Various policies have been formulated to improve access, equity, and sustainability of education for all levels of society, especially vulnerable groups.

1. Educational Assistance Policy

The assistance for education that is quite widely provided is the School Operational Assistance (BOS) fund or what is now known as the Education Unit Operational Assistance (BOSP). The government's main effort in reducing the school dropout rate is through providing educational assistance for students from underprivileged families. Programs such as the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP), the Smart Indonesia Card (KIP) aim to ease the burden of education costs so that students can continue their education. Based on Fadillah's research, the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP) and School Operational Assistance (BOS) have proven effective as affirmative policies in reducing the number of out-of-school children (ATS) and increasing the Gross Participation Rate (APK) and Net Participation Rate (APM), especially at the elementary level, with significant contributions such as reducing ATS from 4.6 million children in 2020 and returning thousands of children to school through cash and operational assistance. However, implementation is still faced with obstacles such as delays in disbursement of funds, inaccurate targeting, weak supervision, and regional disparities in the 3T areas, which reduce the efficiency and equity of the program.(Fadillah et al., 2025). The research results show that the implementation of the PIP program is quite effective in preventing school dropouts, although challenges remain, such as uneven distribution and suboptimal administration. This indicates that the financial assistance has had a positive impact, but its implementation still requires improvement.

2. Free and Compulsory Education Policy

Governmentalso implemented a free education policy through a 12-year compulsory education program that aims to provide equal educational opportunities for all school-age children. In a study by Sutisna et al., in Cilegon City, the implementation of this policy was proven to be able to reduce the dropout rate, although the results were not fully optimal because they were still influenced by various internal and external factors of the students. This confirms that the free education policy is an important instrument in increasing educational participation. The government's seriousness towards the world of education in Cilegon City in its efforts to reduce the number of children dropping out of school through free education is proven by the fact that as many as 305 children in Cilegon City who had dropped out of school have now been returned by the Cilegon City Education and Culture Office through the sekole maning lur movement program.(HG Sutisna et al., 2025).

Some of the policies of the Wajo Regency government above, in reducing the number of school dropouts that occur in Wajo Regency, according to the author, the policy of completing 12 years of compulsory education in the form of a circular from the Wajo Regency Government with various supporting programs that have not been optimally realized, this occurs because there are still The condition of children who drop out of school in Wajo Regency. Good coordination and cooperation between the relevant local government parties, in this case the Sub-district and Village/Lurah, with the Education Office are the main factors in socializing the completion of 12 years of compulsory education

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as a form of the importance of education for every child to improve the quality of society which is not yet evenly distributed, as seen from the fact that there are still people who do not know about this. but (Fauzi et al., 2014)

3. Regional-Based Policy and Political Will

The success of education policies is also largely determined by the commitment, or political will, of local governments. Local governments play a crucial role in designing programs tailored to local needs and conditions. In Central Bangka Regency, this commitment is realized through various programs such as scholarships, educational facility development, and the implementation of inclusive education policies. This demonstrates that planned and sustainable interventions can contribute to reducing dropout rates. Based on Fauzi's research, in Wajo Regency, the government has taken strategic action by establishing new schools in remote areas lacking adequate educational facilities. These schools are designed to meet local needs, such as the availability of teachers, learning resources, and other supporting infrastructure. The goal of building these schools is to achieve equal access to education, so that children in remote areas can receive an education more easily. (Fauzi et al., 2014). In Sukabumi City, the Education Office has implemented several strategic policies, such as the Dropout Tracking Program (PAPS) to reach students who have dropped out or are at risk of dropping out, family mentoring, strengthening the Equivalency Education program, and mapping areas prone to APS. The implementation process involves the UPTD (Regional Technical Implementation Unit), guidance counselors, school principals, village officials, neighborhood associations (RT/RW), and community leaders, and is supported by the development of standard operating procedures (SOPs) for handling APS, which are disseminated to all educational units. (A. Sutisna et al., 2025)

4. Data Collection and Social Intervention Policy

Strengthening data collection systems and direct intervention for dropouts are also important policies. Programs such as dropout tracking and family support are being implemented to ensure children regain access to education. Research in Sukabumi shows that the dropout tracking program (PAPS), equivalency education, and family mentoring are effective strategies for addressing dropout. However, the main challenges lie in data accuracy and inter-agency coordination, which still need to be improved. The Education Office has implemented several strategic policies, such as the Dropout Tracking Program (PAPS) to reach dropouts or those at risk of dropping out, family mentoring, strengthening the Equivalency Education program, and mapping areas prone to APS. The implementation process involves UPTD (Regional Technical Implementation Unit), guidance counselors, school principals, village officials, neighborhood associations (RT/RW), and community leaders, and is supported by the development of standard operating procedures (SOPs) for handling APS, which are disseminated to all educational units. (A. Sutisna et al., 2025).

5. Multi-Sector Collaboration

Government policies will not be implemented optimally without support from various parties. Therefore, collaboration between the government, the community, and the private sector is key to reducing the school dropout rate. A multisectoral approach through collaboration with the community and relevant agencies has proven to have a positive impact on reducing the number of children dropping out of school. This demonstrates the importance of synergy between stakeholders for the successful implementation of education policies.

Meanwhile, in East Nusa Tenggara (NTT), Henriquez's research revealed the existence of the Sanggar Kegiatan Belajar (SKB) program to address school dropout. The SKB's equal education policy targets groups facing multidimensional barriers, including social, economic, and psychological barriers. As a corrective measure, the SKB provides opportunities for students who have dropped out of school to return to educational services. (Henriquez, 2025). In Kalosi Alau Village, Sidenreng Rappang Regency, South Sulawesi, the local government not only functions as a policy maker, but also a facilitator connecting various stakeholders, including village governments, schools, parents, and non-governmental organizations. Substantively, the steps taken by the local government include providing alternative education (Kejar Paket A/B/C), the "Pick Up School Children" program, providing scholarships, and transportation subsidies. (Hasanah et al., 2024).

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CONCLUSION

Based on various research findings, it can be concluded that the causes of school dropout are complex and multidimensional, involving economic, social, cultural, individual factors, and educational policy. These factors are interrelated and influence students' decisions to continue or discontinue their education. The most dominant factor is the family's economic situation. Financial limitations prevent many children from low-income families from continuing their education, despite various forms of government assistance. Furthermore, children often have to work to support their families, making education a marginalized priority. Furthermore, the family and social environment also play a significant role. Lack of parental attention, low levels of education within the family, and a less harmonious family environment can dampen a child's enthusiasm for learning. A less supportive community environment also increases the risk of dropping out of school. Culturally, there are still values that undermine the importance of education, such as the practice of early marriage, the view that school is not the most important thing, and the demands of certain social roles, especially for girls. These values indirectly encourage children to leave school early.

Furthermore, internal individual factors also play a role, such as low motivation to learn, peer influence, and a lack of interest in education. These factors are often reinforced by an unfavorable environment. Furthermore, educational policies and systems contribute, such as limited access to education, inadequate facilities and infrastructure, unequal distribution of aid, and a weak data collection system for students at risk of dropping out. Overall, school dropout is not caused by a single factor, but rather the result of an interaction of various factors. Therefore, addressing it requires a comprehensive, integrated, and sustainable approach involving the government, families, and the community. Government policies to reduce the school dropout rate encompass various aspects, ranging from educational assistance, free education, strengthening the role of local governments, to social interventions and multi-sector collaboration. Overall, these policies have demonstrated positive impacts in reducing the dropout rate. However, their effectiveness still faces various obstacles, such as uneven distribution of aid, budget constraints, and data collection issues. Therefore, strengthened policy implementation, improved coordination, and program innovation are needed to ensure optimal and sustainable dropout reduction efforts.

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